

Creating historic modern cities, by learning from modern historic cities*

'O Novo Mundo já não é este lado do Atlântico, nem tampouco o outro lado do Pacífico. O Novo Mundo não está à esquerda nem à direita, mas em cima de nós; precisamos elevar o espírito para alcançá-lo, pois já não é uma questão de espaço, porém de tempo, de evolução e de maturidade. O Novo Mundo é agora a Nova Era, e cabe à inteligência retomar o seu comando.' Lúcio Costa, *Módulo* (1987) 93, 18.

'The New World is no longer restricted to this side of the Atlantic Ocean, or the other side of the Pacific. The New World does not lay to our left nor to our right, but can be found above us, we should lift our mind to reach it, as it is no longer a matter of space, but rather of time, of evolution and maturity. The New World is now the New Age, and it is up to the intellect to recover its command.' Lúcio Costa, *Módulo* (1987) 93, 18.

The New Age has arrived in the Netherlands. Globalization, mobility, individualization and virtual reality play an important role in contemporary daily life. Still, this part of the Old World does not just live the New Age alone. The ever stressed and hurrying Dutch also seek 'mental resting points', like landmarks and memory anchors. There is big public support for the preservation of monuments, historic towns, landscapes and nature reserves. Hundreds of private and public organizations with millions of members act in the field of nature and monument preservation. The popularity of these organizations is hard to match with that other national passion: the rush for economic growth and prosperity, mani-

fest in large houses, big cars, wide speedways and an extensive leisure and service structure. In this context, the simultaneous desires for innovation and preservation cause tensions in the built environment. The fragile balance between rupture (longing for the new) and continuity (sticking to the old) is reflected in planning, thus drawing up the outlines of a past and a future in the cities.

How should the CIAM-based postwar neighbourhoods be treated in this respect? The tendency is to tear them all down and substitute them for new neighbourhoods with a stronger identity, human scale and personality. Instead of the traditional and moralistic discourse to (over-)estimate their artistic, historic and cultural value (it will take decades to change the current public opinion), a better strategy to invert this tendency is to stress their potential to be transformed into areas full of identity, human scale and personality, as unique components of the postmodern network cities. In the past, a similar transformation took place in the inner cities. We can learn from this process, which took place from the late 19th Century onwards and was - surprise - conducted by modern architects and planners.

The quest for identity

The (re-)development of urban sites brings about a search for 'local identity'. Apparently, identity can be invented. What is actually meant with the term 'identity of the built environment' is hard to say, it is a feature that transforms 'space' into 'place': a unique setting in which people can feel at home. The challenge to create identity is biggest in anonymous peripheries, where monotonous residential areas, gray business districts, large urban development areas and small green areas can be found. Sometimes history provides a basis for the creation of a specific spatial layout, for instance when country estates, ancient defense lines or monumental infrastructure can direct and be incorporated into new urban plans. Landscape can also bring local identity into urban plans, although The Netherlands have little to offer in this respect: some lakes, bushes, open areas and canals. On sites that lack clearly defined and visible physical features, identity has to be 'invented'. The new context can derive from new functions, as is the case in the surroundings of the XXL football stadium of Ajax in the periphery of Amsterdam. Other options are to create an artificial context with narrative urbanism (practiced in The Netherlands for instance by the urban planner Ashok Bhalotra) or to re-write history, a very popular planning tool that has already resulted in 21st Century castles with luxurious apartments and brand-new historic country estates filled with ordinary family homes. All the efforts to create an identity have

one disadvantage: they often only lead to theatrical settings. The functions stay homogeneous, the use is monotonous and the mix of average citizens is the same as in any suburb anywhere else. Faked identities suggest an anchor, a superficial tie between resident and residence.

Historic cities

Faced with the challenge to create urban areas with an 'identity', one is tempted to consider the CIAM-based postwar urban extensions and the historic inner cities as bad and good examples respectively. The differences between them are considerable. The inner cities have numerous historic layers, they bear traces of centuries of human activity and feature a mix of functions. The urban fabric is compiled out of individual constructions into a continuous building mass in which the public space is left open. The human scale, the spatial diversity and the picturesque appearance make up attractive environments for living, working and leisure. New buildings can be incorporated easily into the townscape, complementing the dominant context with either contemporary or historic forms. The tourist potential of the inner cities proves their well defined character, the pleasant atmosphere is a basis for an entire industry of tourism and leisure that has developed in the historic districts. Eventually the old towns have become the logotypes of the big modern cities that have developed around them, their visual identity is scaled up to large urban regions.

Postwar extensions

Postwar neighbourhoods lack, just like many older urban extensions, the historic layers of the inner cities. They have homogeneous economic profiles and spatial structures and offer a poor mix of functions. The townscape is built up out of large volumes that stand solitary in a continuous open space. Similar neighbourhoods are spread over around the country: if you have seen one, you have seen them all. The large scale and the monotony cause disorientation and add to unfriendly public spaces. Visitors are a rare species in these areas, they can be recognized by the detailed maps they carry around in order not to get lost.

The future of these neighbourhoods, that were built in large numbers with small budgets, is now being discussed. Conceived as strongholds for a better world to come, many of these urban complexes barely made it to the year 2000. A large number of buildings urgently needs structural repairs and the apartments are considered too small. Besides, the housing stock of these neighbourhoods is too homogeneous to attend to the current demands and the use and maintenance of the vast public space

has become problematic. The collective services and centers do not correspond to today's requirements of the individualistic and heterogeneous user profile and security seems to be hard to deal with. These and other factors make town planners and developers argue that reforms are necessary and in many cases that demolition is inevitable. In all the big cities a number of blocks has been erased already. The new Housing Act (2000) estimates that 500.000 dwellings of the postwar housing stock (equivalent to 7,5% of the country's total dwelling stock) will have to be substituted.

The modern city at age

If Dutch common sense would prevail, it would be acknowledged that the (anonymous) planners of the Middle Ages and the Golden Age (17th Century) would have been more capable to face the challenges of 21st Century urbanism than the planners of the 20th Century. But of course, it is all too simple to praise the inner cities with their mixed functions and the tiny urban fabric, and to condemn the urban extensions with their rigid separation of functions and the open urban layout. Is demolition the most likely future for modern towns and neighbourhoods? There are utilitarian, conceptual and historic arguments to plea for a careful examination of the opportunities to recycle modern town planning, rather than eliminating it on forehand.

The utilitarian argument is simple: as long as existing structures can be partly or largely integrated into new solutions, a waste of material, energy and sometimes money can be prevented. New designs and architectonic, technical and typological solutions can bring up innovative architecture that adds value to the contemporary building production. The conceptual argument deals with the concern about these 'problematic' areas and the desire to substitute them by areas with more variety, identity and human scale. It seems to be controversial to erase the only historic layer of the urban extensions and start from scratch, subsequently trying to create in artificial ways new identities by faking a history that never was. The problem of the suburbs is not their concept, but rather their poor and homogeneous elaboration. Arming the existing urban fabric and the architectonic structures with new uses and users, mixing functions, establishing new centers and public spaces and introducing new typologies can lead to genuine modern areas: modern in concept, updated in functions and enriched and matured over time.

The historic argument to reconsider the future of the extensive urban extensions from the 1950s and 1960s is not that they are unique, bare the memories of an important time and reflect important cultural values and architectural principles. They are

all but unique, although some blocks and urban plans may have exceptional qualities. As we are talking large numbers and massive areas it seems to be mediocre and irrelevant to use qualifications of monument-worthiness.

The historic argument has nothing to do with the way modern architects faced the future of their work as well. They became known for stating that functional architecture without adequate functions should be demolished and that their creations should never be an exception to this. Nobody ever wondered if the architects of churches and palaces in the Middle Ages and later ever agreed with the transformation of their work in tourist attractions and pleasure domes. How the modern architects looked at the future is part of a contemporary discourse that has little to do with the actual debate on the city. *They* are not in charge with the planning in the 21st Century, but we are. If we valorize non-functional functionalism for other than purely utilitarian reasons, we have the full right to do so. The historic argument to cherish postwar neighbourhoods that is presented here is that we can learn from history how to transform and adapt 'problematic' urban areas for new uses, without losing their architectonic and urban features. In this respect we should not study how modern architects faced the future one hundred years ago, but how they faced the past.

Image

The inner cities that nowadays are considered amongst the most wanted living and working spaces, have little in common with the situation that existed there around the year 1900. A look at the ancient pictures, reveals that even Amsterdam was a dull town one day. The images transmit a provincial atmosphere and a narrow minded attitude. The variety of architecture, functions, scales and lifestyles that nowadays make up the charm and the image of the city were not existing by then. In that recent past, there was hardly any positive appreciation for historic towns. They were considered to be a source of diseases and a place of human decay. The smell of the polluted canals and the polluting industry must have been disgusting. Modern traffic jammed the old streets and the overcrowded residential areas were in need of demolition and reconstruction. From the end of the 19th Century onwards, sanitation engineers, architects and housing specialist all asked for radical interventions in the inner cities. Historians agreed, as long as the existing monuments and sites were not demolished accidentally.

The paintings of G.H. Breitner show the tremendous impact of the interventions in the old cities. The historic parts of Amsterdam and the other large cities in Holland faced profound reconstruction on

behalf of traffic improvement, substitution of functions, the creation of a modern city-core, building activities and monument preservation. Nevertheless, the old pictures and paintings of the old towns that were produced around 1900 can still easily be identified for anyone who is slightly familiar with today's situation in these towns. Except for the downtown of Rotterdam, which was largely destroyed during World War II, all the old towns in The Netherlands managed to stay themselves while they transformed into modern city centers.

Re-invention

The negative image of the Dutch inner cities one hundred years ago can be compared to the image of the postwar suburbs today. The subsequent question is obvious: can the decaying suburbs undergo a similar improvement of their image as the city centers experienced over the last Century? It is challenging to think of strategies to change these areas into consolidated ensembles which attract residents and investors. As for their size and homogeneous functional and spatial structures, it will be hard to stick rigidly to the existing form. In a gradual process of development, differentiation, densification, mixing of functions and renewal, these areas can gain a new spirit and an economic input, without losing their specific features.

There is no need to pull down all the decaying blocks at once, if a part remains it offers cheap dwellings and may - sooner or later - open opportunities to accommodate programs that do not exist today, just like what happened with abandoned warehouses, schools and workers homes in the inner cities. As long as massive demolition prevails, we might get state of the art neighbourhoods with a very varied architecture and green structures, but with a one dimensional soul, an identity of superficial forms.

Of course it is unthinkable that the urban extensions can be transformed into historic inner cities. They have an open layout and a different scale, they are dimensioned to accommodate trains and cars, date from another era and will never contain the functions that are clustered in the traditional downtown.

Yet, a transformation process might take place that shows similarities to the transformation of the old towns in modern city centers over the last 100 years. Not the comparison of the historic center and the suburbs in terms of design or functional program is relevant, but rather the conceptual approach matters: a unprejudiced interpretation of the existing situation, development of new functional programs, the search for architectonic and urbanistic adaptations to new requirements and tendencies, as well as the creative process to bring a new spirit into areas with proper characteristics. Identities do

not have to be invented, the modern city itself should be re-invented.

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